
| RESEARCH ARTICLE

Use of Genres: Classroom Teaching Frequency and Usefulness in the Workplace.

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| ABSTRACT

Genres are integral to and critically important for any ESP writing course. As part of the needs analysis to design an ESP writing course, classroom teaching frequency and professional usefulness of writing genres for engineering students were matched and correlated. The four groups comprising students, teachers, operational and managerial engineers were compared in terms of their responses to the teaching and usefulness of genres. Accordingly, post hoc analysis was carried out, and means were compared wherever the differences were found to be significant. It has been established through this research that needs analysis of all the important stakeholders- students, professional engineers, teachers – should be done because there are gaps in their respective perceptions regarding the use of genres in an ESP course and through such a triangulated assessment, the gaps can be minimized.

| KEYWORDS

Needs analysis, engineers, engineering students, ESP, genres, writing skills.

| ARTICLE INFORMATION

ACCEPTED: 25 July 2023

PUBLISHED: 02 August 2023

DOI: 10.32996/ijllt.2023.6.8.6

1. Introduction

This research was part of my dissertation work. To design and implement a new writing course for first-year engineering students from six colleges in West Bengal, an elaborate needs analysis was carried out. The views of the engineering students, the ESP (English for Specific Purpose) teachers, and the professional engineers (both operational and managerial) were taken, and an attempt was made to align the views of all these stakeholders to make the writing course of the classroom to reflect as much and as far as possible the professional needs of the engineers. Any writing course will always have genres at its core. This paper specifically focuses on the findings related to classroom teaching of genres and its application in the workplace.

1.1 The Specificity of English and ESP

Regarding language for specific purposes Gollin- Kies et al. raise a fundamental question in order to explain the difference between language and language for specific purposes.

“Does the difference, if it exists, reside in the specialised vocabulary used, in the different meanings ascribed to words in different contexts, in the different collocations, in the way that sentences and ideas are sequenced and combined to form a coherent communicative event, in the interpersonal relations that are realised in the text, in the constraints on what can and cannot be said and on different roles of the event’s participants, in the values that are embedded in the text?” (Gollin- Kies et al. 2016, p.1).

Saber (2016) considers ESP as a variety in a specific social context depending on professional or content-related confines. [Belcher, 2012]. Pettit’s seminal work in 2002 has led Sarré and Whyte (2017) to include the study of not only discourse features

but also the entire gamut of language and culture of a specific group of professionals, along with the didactic study of language learning and teaching within ESP. (p. 150).

Dudley- Evans and John (1998) point out that the chief distinguishing features of ESP are needs and text analysis, and consequently, gravitate toward learning to communicate effectively in the classroom and workplace (p.1). [Dudley-Evans, 1998]. Hutchinson and Waters (2009) first claim that ESP is not any "particular" language, "methodology", or "material" and then arrive at a clear definition and then conclude with the claim that it is an approach which has as its fundamental defining characteristic of learner needs. (p. 19). [Hutchinson, 2009]. However, from all the definitions above, the narrow focus of ESP is clearly understood.

Robinson (1991) argues in her study of the beginnings of ESP that it developed because of (a) global needs, (b) the language revolution, and (c) the student.

Johns and Salmani-Nodoushan (2015) have pointed out that the adult ESP learner spends less time and attention on ESP than on other learning methods because s/he has considerable psychological and social needs to fulfil. They agree, however, that it makes sense to concentrate on learners if it means that they are prepared for their later duties and the requirements to help them in their future careers. In today's world, the field of applied linguistics, known as ESP, is well-established, and its development continues. (Bolton & Jenks, 2022, p.506).

1.2 ESP in India

The most common language in today's world is English, without a doubt. Any development and experience in science, technology, and medicine is available in English. English is considered a vast global language and a core aspect of the postcolonial past of India in the event of India's independence. It is spoken in 101 countries, and it is the connecting language in "international businesses, worldwide diplomacy, and science." (Thierry, 2018). While there is a huge demand in our society for English education, in vernacular medium colleges, the teaching standards are not very satisfactory. Clement and Murugavel (2018) have identified gaps between the teacher's methodology and engineering students' confidence levels.

Chaudhury (2002) argues that as there were Bengali- English and Urdu- English glossaries even in the eighteenth century, the roots of English for specific purposes (ESP) in India could be traced to that time. As per Tasildar (2013), the findings of the Study Group (1971), the Curriculum Development Centre (1989), and the various projects of the British Council in the 80s were mainly responsible for the spread of ESP education in India in the previous century. [44]. The recommendation of the Study Group (1971) to consider "English as a library language" initiated the official journey of ESP in India. It also suggested "a course on commercial English".. Similarly, CDC (1989) proposed courses like "Business Communication" and "English for advertising and copywriting". The British Council's collaboration with the Indian Institute of Mines resulted in English for science and technology. Similarly, its project in Kolkata with the Teachers' Training Institute gave birth to "Communication in English for technical students" in 1984. (Tasildar, 2013, p.4). Upadhyay (2018) shows how ESP courses have flourished in the UK with the option of doing a master's in it in some universities and the fact that ESP has a dedicated international journal. However, Tasildar (2013) rightly points out that beyond a few specialized certificate courses offered by a few universities, only two courses, "Technical English", and "Business English", satisfy the workplace needs of budding engineers and business management students in India respectively have dominated). So, there are immense possibilities in ESP teaching/ learning, including designing courses, in India.

Engineering colleges and technical institutions have grown considerably in the past four decades in India. The four southern states alone generate approximately 75% of the country's population, which is higher than the United States. (Singh & Solanki, 2016).

Today, India produces the largest number of engineers in the world annually. As per Thakur and Mantha (2021), one million engineers graduate in India every year from "3500 engineering colleges, 3400 polytechnics, and 200 schools of planning and architecture."

1.3 Writing As a Skill.

Writing may be viewed as a communication mechanism where the readers may receive a message through a traditional graphic method. It is a productive skill. (Hyland, 2013, p.95) signifies the importance of writing; thus, "Not only is it hard to imagine modern academic and corporate life without essays, commercial letters, emails, medical reports and minutes of meetings, but writing is also a key feature of every student's experience.". Hyland (2003) points out that writing skill is the toughest challenge for teachers. A second language learner must acquire extensive linguistic competence to be able to write successfully. Teachers need to use controlled activities, authentic tasks and real-life experiences to improve the writing of the learners. (Swales & Feak, 2012). A mother tongue and second language are most unlikely to have the same patterning of arrangement and outlining to present ideas and opinions, and the earlier experiences of the learners at home or in school do not make them properly attuned to academic and workplace writing needs. (Hyland, 2013, p.96).

1.3.1 Writing Skill: Various Approaches

The teaching of writing contains three main approaches: (1) Product, (2) Process, and (3) Genre. In diverse learning contexts, blended methods are now common since they incorporate the strengths of all three.

1.3.1.1 Product Approach.

This approach focuses on language knowledge, vocabulary, grammar, and unified instruments (Pincas, 1982). The grammar of the language is primarily taught. The words "text-based technique" and "ordered composition" are used to support this approach. Initially, the students are provided with texts to be taught. The students progressively exercise the complexities of writing skills in the regulated and directed writing stage. The students are finally prepared to write for free.

1.3.1.2 Process Approach.

This strategy focuses mainly on preparation, composition, and drafting instead of the commodity approach. Language knowledge is less emphasized. Tribble (2005) describes the four phases of writing as a) prewriting, b) composition/design, and c) evaluating and structuring editing.[47]. It is also a "cyclical" (Bruner, 1962) method in which, even after drafting and reviewing, the author will arrive at the prewriting point. Teachers are acting as facilitators in this strategy. They do not have the requisite information for the writing activity but use brainstorming as a powerful strategy to connect concepts to the subject selected for the writing activity. Teachers prepare, write and draft the text during the brainstorming session.

1.3.1.3 Genre Approaches.

Like product approaches, the genre approach often offers linguistic awareness as a priority and is named "product approach extension" since it parallels the product approach. However, the focus on the social sense is the unique feature of the genre approach. This "social sense" component allows curriculum developers to determine the corresponding written forms for students. For example, the Information Technology curriculum focuses on appropriate texts for their work conditions. Social meaning, which is an additional technique in the genre approach, is not granted in commodity approaches.

As Dudley- Evans (1997) mentions, the genre method has three steps. A model genre text is provided for interpretation in the first step. The students then perform the lessons based on the latter. The students in the final level create a short text.

This model will reveal that the approach of genres is not entirely different from the product approach. The genre approach, though, varies from the product approach, as it emphasizes issues such as communication objectives, social situations, and audience-writer interaction.

Swales' genre analysis approach (1990) has never asserted that EGP (English for General Purposes) and ESP are two distinct languages; in fact, they have interconnected skills. In the 1990s, Swales defined "communicative intent" as the main character determining if a given text was an example of a specific genre. According to him, texts can be treated in three ways: (1) they can be used for several purposes, (2) they can be used for multiple purposes, and (3) they may be used for many purposes at once. If a genre has identical language and rhetorical characteristics, it does not always mean that it has the same communication purpose. (Swales & Rogers, 1995). Swales (2004) mentions that goal of language learning is not static; it may evolve. The communication aims of a text are tied to its textual category, which may be used for a variety of reasons across cultures.

Similarly, Bhatia (2004) defines "gender colonies" as genres with the same communication goal in various occupations, fields, and user settings.[4]. Johns (2008), too, argues that for both her writer and her audience, a single work in a genre might fulfil a variety of functions; she further argues that it can no longer be stated that a text of a certain kind exists a one-to-one connection between that text and that purpose. It is thus impossible to separate an ESP from EGP linguistically, but only in terms of genre, task, goal, and context. As Hymes (1974) correctly pointed out, each competent language user assesses and selects a suitable code that serves the linguistic circumstance.

Chapelle (1998) and Douglas (2000) walk-in altogether different paths. The former argues for a theory to account for how particular situations (in a Language for a Specific Academic Purpose context) within the broader culture (Communicative Language Ability) constrain a linguistic user to apply his/ her choice of a linguistic item. (p. 15). Likewise, Douglas (2000) claims that it is probably the knowledge base that differentiates Language for Specific Purposes from other kinds of language learning. However, both Chapelle (1998) and Douglas (2000) do not provide empirical evidence to back their claims.

As teaching is demanding, a versatile writing method at the tertiary level is quite helpful. The benefits and disadvantages of each strategy will always be there. Furthermore, all the written methods are complimentary. With the complexities of written skills, the instructor will teach writing by a comprehensive methodology that combines the main valuable facets. The Badger & White (2000)

approach to process genres is an example of an interconnected approach that includes nuances of product and process approaches.

1.3.1.4 Genre-Reliant Teaching.

White and Arndt's (1991) process approach has been criticized because it ignores (a) the distinctive needs of writing assignments and (b) changes in different written circumstances are not addressed (Paltridge & Starfield, 2014) and ultimately, such criticisms paved the way for the genre-based instructional process. Hyon (2017) agrees that genres help learners to use language patterns in "target contexts."

Critics of genre-based approaches have raised questions regarding their efficacy because they are excessively product-based and presume established text patterns; they also questioned the genre-based approach, claiming that it encouraged students to hunt for predefined formulas and fixed patterns, which may ultimately divorce them from naturalness in writing. Flowerdew (1993) attempts to integrate process and genre-based education. His other main point is the distinction between a genre-based education and a results-based education. Johns (2008) finds merit in this approach owing to two reasons (1) genre sensitivity and (2) acquisition of genres. The first ensures that students learn skills and methods to address different new circumstances and tasks; the second ensures that they get the necessary professional abilities to execute their jobs.

However, some warn us of the potential dangers of "genres of power" taught via a genre-based method. In professional societies, genres of power may be characterized as discursive and acknowledged language acts, the goal of which is to establish authority and power imbalance. Extensive genre education gives students the resources they need to create their professional abilities and prepares them for their professional engagement in their envisioned target community (Belcher, 2012)

Hyland (2022) considers genre analysis as "one of the most important items in the ESP toolbox" (p.6). Freddi and Tluková (2022) feel that knowledge of a genre enables an ESP user specialist knowledge to communicate with the academic and professional world in a more effective and efficient way. (p.37). Knowledge of genre can help in a better grasp of rhetorical structures and collocational patterns, and these are fundamental to developing the writing skills of engineering students. (Noguchi & Kunioshi, 2022)

Genre teaching and learning has established its centralist role in ESP need analysis and course design. Hence, it is imperative that there should be a connection between what is expected in professional life with what is taught in engineering colleges.

2. Literature Review

Sukmawati and Nasution (2020) designed research to enhance student writing skills by following a genre-based approach (GBA) for budding computer engineering students in South Indonesia. Students from the university undertook Classroom Action Research in two cycles. Reading tests, observations, and questionnaires were used to verify the results. The test outcome showed that GBA implementation increased the average class score in cycle one from 54 to 59.95. The commitment and motivation of the learning method, as suggested by questionnaires and observations, respectively, accompanied this development. In addition, the average score increased from 59.5 to 70.5 with Cycle 2 implementation. This increase in performance was accompanied by the agility and collaboration of the students during the education period. This study concluded that the use of GBA would boost students' writing skills. Robinson and Blair (1995) taught writing skills to first-year students at Edinburgh University in a professional engineering module. The overall class sizes and relatively poor writing standards of the native English speakers at the beginning of the course posed difficulties. It aimed to give students the ability to collaborate with any lecturer easily and learn engineering writing conventions. Writer-centric, genre-centric, and reader-oriented were emphasized in all four years of the course. A questionnaire, student interviews, and feedback interpretation program measured the merits of seminars and presentations. The researchers concluded that structured input was an indicator that helped students build and sustain a professional growth curriculum to increase their abilities in writing to the degree that fitted their profession's needs. Changpueng and Pattanapichet (2015) aimed to explore the needs of managers, organizational engineers, ESP professors, and Thailand engineering students. The written correspondence demands made on engineers in their jobs, including an investigation of meaning and circumstance, were collected by questionnaire surveys and interviews. These findings allowed the author to produce educational resources to assist the workplace needs of engineers.

3. Method

3.1 Research questions

Is there any significant difference between the different groups in terms of the frequency of writing tasks/ genres in the ESP classroom?

Is there any significant difference between the different groups in terms of the perceived usefulness of writing tasks/ genres in the ESP classroom?

3.2 Participants

Four hundred students studying in the first year in six different colleges in West Bengal under Maulana Abul Kalam Azad University of Technology after completing the English course provided in the first semester, 22 language instructors teaching language skills at different engineering colleges in West Bengal were administered a questionnaire. In addition, 55 operational engineers and 26 managerial engineers were also part of this triangulated study. The rationale was that the views and opinions of those who use the language were needed to compare and correlate with the present classroom teaching/ learning. The rationale was that the views and opinions of those who use the language were needed to compare and correlate with the present classroom teaching/ learning. The colleges were chosen to comply with certain conditions. Firstly, the average English scores in the first semester university exam of the engineering students of these six colleges at the MAKAUT were higher than the average scores of the students of most other engineering colleges in the eastern region under the same university. That this category would prove to be more responsive and inclusive of foreign intervention in their classroom was the rationale for the incorporation of purposive sampling in the sample frame. The other important stakeholders- the teachers and professional engineers (operational and managerial) were chosen as well to reduce the gulf between the formal instructional setting and the workplace as much as possible.

3.3 Instrument(s)

To conduct formal research, a questionnaire is quite often used. It is often regarded as one of the greatest ways to back up our results in research. Remote discussion between the researcher and the responder also took place through this instrument. To make the questionnaire useful and relevant, the respondents were made to answer questions that were relevant and necessary to the study. For the responders to know what they are supposed to answer, the test's guidelines and instructions were made clear after piloting and discussion with peers and my supervisor. To avoid any misunderstandings, all the instructions, including the purpose of the study, were offered upfront. A lot of attention was paid to making the questions follow a logical structure to allow for rational responses from the participants. 'Close-ended' and 'open ended' questions were asked. Though there were seven dimensions in my research related to ESP writing course design, viz. motivation and attitude toward English materials, methodology, existing course, genre, current writing ability, and need and expectation from the new course, the present article shows the findings related to genre analysis. Some of the ways through which the research was sought to be made statistically reliable are as follows:

- Two previously implemented questionnaires, one from India (Neelaveni, 2005, Appendixes I & II) and another from abroad (Basturkmen, 2010, pp.30-31), were adapted to maintain consistency.
- Tests, before and after the course, were conducted along the lines of old Cambridge exams. Both tests were made to test the same writing genres and had the same level of difficulty. There was a gap of around six months between the two tests, so the chances of students relying on memory were remote. The genres were the same but not the contents.
- Questionnaires for engineering students, professional engineers (ex-engineering students) and teachers had certain common elements.

Discussions with subject experts and experienced faculty members ensured face validity. Further, the pilot- test also lent validity to the survey instrument.

3.4 Questionnaire Design

To conduct formal research, a questionnaire is quite often used. It is often regarded as one of the greatest ways to back up our results in research. Remote discussion between the researcher and the responder also took place through this instrument. To make the questionnaire useful and relevant, the respondents were made to answer questions that were relevant and necessary to the study. For the responders to know what they are supposed to answer, the test's guidelines and instructions were made clear after piloting and discussion with peers and my supervisor. To avoid any misunderstandings, all the instructions, including the purpose of the study, were offered upfront. A lot of attention was paid to making the questions follow a logical structure to allow for rational responses from the participants. 'Close-ended' and 'open ended' questions were asked. Though there were seven dimensions in my research related to ESP writing course design, viz. motivation and attitude toward English materials,

methodology, existing course, genre, current writing ability, and need and expectation from the new course, the present article shows the findings related to genre analysis.

3.5 Assessments and Measures

The questionnaires were adapted from Basturkmen (2010, pp.30-31). [2]. Through survey questionnaires with respondents, data were gathered. Coolican (1994) advocates the use of Likert scales because of their higher reliability and validity.[11]. Data acquired were analyzed using tests like ANOVA, Tukey’s post hoc using SPSS software and Kruskal- Wallis, the non-parametric equivalent of ANOVA and rank correlations using R (4.0.5.) to arrive at accurate and acceptable conclusions

4. Results

4.1 Results of comparative analysis

Table 1

Showing Results of ANOVA Test

Laboratory reports	Between Groups	3.886	2	1.943	3.294	.038
	Within Groups	280.732	476	.590		
	Total	284.618	478			
Technical reports	Between Groups	7.079	2	3.540	5.707	.004
	Within Groups	295.251	476	.620		
	Total	302.330	478			
Manuals	Between Groups	.287	2	.144	.220	.803
	Within Groups	310.777	476	.653		
	Total	311.065	478			
Research articles	Between Groups	5.794	2	2.897	5.445	.005
	Within Groups	253.241	476	.532		

	Total	259.035	478			
Job applications	Between Groups	2.216	2	1.108	1.779	.170
	Within Groups	296.477	476	.623		
	Total	298.693	478			
Resume writing	Between Groups	10.542	2	5.271	7.459	.001
	Within Groups	336.385	476	.707		
	Total	346.927	478			
Expository writing (explaining/ describing)	Between Groups	30.188	2	15.094	24.491	.000
	Within Groups	292.743	475	.616		
	Total	322.931	477			
Essay assignments	Between Groups	.230	2	.115	.187	.829
	Within Groups	292.563	476	.615		
	Total	292.793	478			
Letters/ emails	Between Groups	13.271	2	6.636	12.429	.000
	Within Groups	254.119	476	.534		

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	Total	267.390	478			
Summary writing	Between Groups	5.429	2	2.715	5.032	.007
	Within Groups	256.792	476	.539		
	Total	262.221	478			
Minutes	Between Groups	.860	2	.430	.539	.584
	Within Groups	379.983	476	.798		
	Total	380.843	478			
Persuasive writing	Between Groups	14.007	2	7.003	10.669	.000
	Within Groups	311.792	475	.656		
	Total	325.799	477			
Proposal for grants etc.	Between Groups	72.143	2	36.072	62.253	.000
	Within Groups	275.811	476	.579		
	Total	347.954	478			

Note. No. of students= 400, no of operational engineers= 55, no. of managerial engineers=26.

Comparisons between students and professional engineers and between operational and managerial engineers are shown in Table 1 with regard to the teaching frequency of various writing genres.

Figure 1

Means Plots Based on Post-hoc Analysis for the Frequency of the Writing Task/ Genre (Laboratory Reports)

Note. As per Figure 1, the mean scores reflect that in the case of the frequency of the writing task (Laboratory Reports) in the engineering course, the students rated its frequency to be lower in comparison to the ratings submitted by engineers. Within the engineers operational engineers reported a higher frequency of the mentioned writing task in the engineering course.

Figure 2

Means Plots Based on Post-hoc Analysis for the Frequency of the Writing Task/ Genre (Technical Reports).

Note. As per Figure 2, the mean scores reflect that in the case of the frequency of the writing task (Technical Reports) in the engineering course, the students rated its frequency to be lower in comparison to the ratings submitted by engineers. Among the engineers, managerial engineers reported a higher frequency of the mentioned writing task in the engineering course.

Figure 3

Means Plots Based on Post-hoc Analysis for the Frequency of the Writing Task/ Genre (Research Articles)

Note. As per Figure 3, the mean scores reflect that in the case of the frequency of the writing task (Research Articles) in the engineering course, the students rated its frequency to be higher in comparison to the ratings submitted by engineers. As far as the engineers were concerned, both groups (managerial engineers and professional engineers) reported similar frequency of the mentioned writing task.

Figure 4

Means Plots Based on Post-hoc Analysis for the Frequency of the Writing Task/ Genre (Expository Writing)

Note. As per Figure 4, the mean scores reflect that in the case of the frequency of the writing task (Expository Writing) in the engineering course, the students rated its frequency to be lower in comparison to the ratings submitted by engineers. Within the engineers operational engineers reported a higher frequency of the mentioned writing task in the engineering course.

Figure 5

Means Plots Based on Post-hoc Analysis for the Frequency of the Writing Task/ Genre (Letters/ emails)

As per Figure 5, the mean scores reflect that in the case of the frequency of the writing task (Letters/Emails) in the engineering course, the students rated its frequency to be lower in comparison to the ratings submitted by engineers. Within the engineers operational engineers reported a higher frequency of the mentioned writing task in the engineering course.

Figure 6

Means Plots Based on Post-hoc Analysis for the Frequency of the Writing Task/ Genre (Summary Writing)

Note. As per Figure 6, the mean scores reflect that in the case of the frequency of the writing task (Summary Writing) in the engineering course, the students rated its frequency to be lower in comparison to the ratings submitted by engineers. Among the engineers, managerial engineers reported a higher frequency of the mentioned writing task in the engineering course.

Table 2

Results of ANOVA for Grading of the Writing Genres According to Their Frequency of Tasks as Perceived by Different Groups

Writing Genre	Groups				p-Values	
	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers	ANOVA	Kruskal Wallis
Laboratory Reports	2.96	3.05	2.79	2.77	0.079	0.099
Technical Reports	3.19	3.04	2.76	3.18	0.001	0.001
Manuals	2.50	2.33	2.36	2.73	0.169	0.252
Research Articles	2.31	2.29	2.58	2.50	0.015	0.011
Job Applications	2.54	2.36	2.58	2.77	0.157	0.059
Resume Writing	2.81	2.45	2.19	3.18	0.000	0.000
Expository Writing	2.54	3.06	2.26	2.91	0.000	0.000
Essay Assignments	2.54	2.36	2.36	2.68	0.204	0.153
Letters and Email	3.04	3.18	2.69	3.73	0.000	0.000
Summary writing	2.81	2.35	2.30	3.09	0.000	0.000
Notes and Minutes writing	2.50	2.24	2.33	2.68	0.173	0.098
Persuasive Writing	2.00	1.73	2.25	1.82	0.000	0.000
Proposal	1.77	1.36	2.52	1.64	0.000	0.000

Table 3

Results of ANOVA for Grading of the Writing Genres According to Their Professional Usefulness as Perceived by Different Groups

Table-2: Correlation between four groups on frequency of writing task				
	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers
Manageria	1	0.872	0.303	0.93
Operational Engineers		1	0.29	0.833
Students			1	0.125
Teachers				1
Table-3: Correlation between four groups on professional importance of the writing genres				
	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers
Manageria	1	0.745	-0.439	0.239
Operational Engineers		1	-0.302	0.053
Students			1	0.335
Teachers				1

Figure 6

Scatter -Plot Showing the Perceptual Difference between Frequency of Writing Tasks and Their Professional Usefulness.

Note. The frequency of classroom teaching and the perceived usefulness of writing genres are correlated in Figure 6.

Table 4.

All Categories of Respondents and Various Writing Genres

Managerial engineers			
Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	0.358	0.134	0.091
Technical reports	0.096	0.764	0.004
Manuals	0.6	0.029	0.184
Research articles	0.455	0.064	0.136
Job applications	0.309	0.173	0.076
Resume writing	-0.407	0.037	0.169
Expository writing	-0.192	0.261	0.052
Essay assignments	0.099	0.556	0.015
Letters/ emails	-0.015	0.93	0
Summary writing	0.419	0.022	0.2
Notes and Minutes Writing	0.024	0.888	0.001
Persuasive writing	-0.088	0.571	0.014
Proposal for grants etc.	0.397	0.028	0.185
Operational engineers			

Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	0.064	0.651	0.004
Technical reports	0.583	0	0.272
Manuals	0.947	0	0.345
Research articles	0.59	0	0.208
Job applications	0.38	0.002	0.171
Resume writing	0.282	0.018	0.102
Expository writing	0.52	0.002	0.166
Essay assignments	0.776	0	0.274
Letters/ emails	0.906	0	0.401
Summary writing	0.589	0	0.299
Notes and Minutes Writing	0.278	0.052	0.069
Persuasive writing	0.143	0.338	0.017
Proposal for grants etc.	0.192	0.074	0.059
Students			
Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	0.564	0	0.266
Technical reports	0.45	0	0.191
Manuals	0.521	0	0.202
Research articles	0.479	0	0.139
Job applications	0.836	0	0.393
Resume writing	0.643	0	0.242
Expository writing	0.827	0	0.401
Essay assignments	0.532	0	0.171
Letters/ emails	0.582	0	0.224
Summary writing	0.759	0	0.27
Notes and Minutes Writing	0.757	0	0.397
Persuasive writing	0.673	0	0.232
Proposal for grants etc.	0.59	0	0.223
Teachers			
Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	-0.066	0.704	0.007
Technical reports	-0.121	0.505	0.023
Manuals	-0.11	0.645	0.011
Research articles	0.043	0.8	0.003

Job applications	0.123	0.334	0.047
Resume writing	-0.265	0.354	0.043
Expository writing	0.5	0.002	0.386
Essay assignments	0.471	0.026	0.224
Letters/emails	-0.009	0.977	0
Summary writing	0.377	0.063	0.162
Notes and Minutes Writing	0.435	0.009	0.293
Persuasive writing	0.45	0.058	0.168
Proposal for grants etc.	0.333	0.126	0.113

Table 5

Results of ANOVA for Grading of the Writing Genres According to Their Frequency of Tasks as Perceived by Different Groups

Writing Genre	Groups				p-Values	
	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers	ANOVA	Kruskal Wallis
Laboratory reports	2.96	3.05	2.79	2.77	0.079	0.099
Technical reports	3.19	3.04	2.76	3.18	0.001	0.001
Manuals	2.50	2.33	2.36	2.73	0.169	0.252
Research articles	2.31	2.29	2.58	2.50	0.015	0.011
Job applications	2.54	2.36	2.58	2.77	0.157	0.059
Resume writing	2.81	2.45	2.19	3.18	0.000	0.000
Expository writing	2.54	3.06	2.26	2.91	0.000	0.000
Essay assignments	2.54	2.36	2.36	2.68	0.204	0.153
Letters/ emails	3.04	3.18	2.69	3.73	0.000	0.000
Summary writing	2.81	2.35	2.30	3.09	0.000	0.000

Use of Genres: Classroom Teaching Frequency and Usefulness in the Workplace.

Notes and minutes writing	2.50	2.24	2.33	2.68	0.173	0.098
Persuasive writing	2.00	1.73	2.25	1.82	0.000	0.000
Proposal for grants etc.	1.77	1.36	2.52	1.64	0.000	0.000

Note. Genres are graded for all the groups in Table 5.

Table 6

Rank Correlation Matrix Showing the Correlation of Ranks of the Writing Genres According to Their Frequency of Writing Tasks as Perceived by Different Groups

	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers
Managerial Engineers	1.000	0.872	0.303	0.930
Operational Engineers		1.000	0.290	0.833
Students			1.000	0.125
Teachers				1.000

Table 7

Results of ANOVA for Grading of the Writing Genres According to Their Professional Usefulness as Perceived by Different Groups

Writing Genre	Groups				p-Values	
	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers	ANOVA	Kruskal Wallis
Laboratory reports	3.08	2.09	3.24	3.59	0.000	0.000
Technical reports	3.81	3.78	3.00	3.59	0.000	0.000
Manuals	3.50	3.76	2.69	2.77	0.000	0.000

Research articles	3.23	3.31	2.94	2.86	0.020	0.020
Job applications	3.27	3.18	2.96	3.09	0.208	0.168
Resume writing	3.35	3.22	2.74	3.36	0.000	0.000
Expository writing	3.42	3.69	2.56	2.95	0.000	0.000
Essay assignments	3.27	2.55	2.87	3.14	0.009	0.003
Letters/ emails	4.35	3.89	2.86	3.82	0.000	0.000
Summary writing	3.58	3.22	2.87	3.27	0.000	0.000
Notes and minute writing	3.42	3.16	2.66	2.95	0.000	0.000
Persuasive writing	3.69	3.62	2.73	2.32	0.000	0.000
Proposal for grants etc.	3.19	3.18	2.95	2.05	0.000	0.000

Table 8.

Rank Correlation Matrix Showing the Correlations of Ranks of the Writing Genres According to Their Professional Usefulness as Perceived by Different Groups

	Managerial Engineers	Operational Engineers	Students	Teachers
Managerial Engineers	1.000	0.745	-0.439	0.239
Operational Engineers		1.000	-0.302	0.053
Students			1.000	0.335
Teachers				1.000

Figure 7

Scatter -plot Regarding Perceptual Difference Between the Frequency of Tasks and Perceived Usefulness for Different Writing Genres.

Table 9

Regression of Professional Usefulness on Frequency of Tasks Among the Managerial Engineers (All Writing Genres)

Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	0.358	0.134	0.091
Technical reports	0.096	0.764	0.004
Manuals	0.600	0.029	0.184
Research articles	0.455	0.064	0.136
Job applications	0.309	0.173	0.076
Resume writing	-0.407	0.037	0.169

Expository writing	-0.192	0.261	0.052
Essay assignments	0.099	0.556	0.015
Letters/ emails	-0.015	0.930	0.000
Summary writing	0.419	0.022	0.200
Note and minutes writing	0.024	0.888	0.001
Persuasive writing	-0.088	0.571	0.014
Proposal for grants etc.	0.397	0.028	0.185

Table 10

Regression of Professional Usefulness on Frequency of Tasks Among the Operational Engineers (All Writing Genres)

Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	0.064	0.651	0.004
Technical reports	0.583	0.000	0.272
Manuals	0.947	0.000	0.345
Research articles	0.590	0.000	0.208
Job applications	0.380	0.002	0.171
Resume writing	0.282	0.018	0.102
Expository writing	0.520	0.002	0.166
Essay assignments	0.776	0.000	0.274
Letters/ emails	0.906	0.000	0.401
Summary writing	0.589	0.000	0.299

Notes and minutes writing	0.278	0.052	0.069
Persuasive writing	0.143	0.338	0.017
Proposal for grants etc.	0.192	0.074	0.059

Table 11

Regression of Professional Usefulness on Frequency of Tasks Among the Students (All Writing Genres)

Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	0.564	0.000	0.266
Technical reports	0.450	0.000	0.191
Manuals	0.521	0.000	0.202
Research articles	0.479	0.000	0.139
Job applications	0.836	0.000	0.393
Resume writing	0.643	0.000	0.242
Expository writing	0.827	0.000	0.401
Essay assignments	0.532	0.000	0.171
Letters/ emails	0.582	0.000	0.224
Summary writing	0.759	0.000	0.270
Notes and minutes writing	0.757	0.000	0.397
Persuasive writing	0.673	0.000	0.232
Proposal for grants etc.	0.590	0.000	0.223

Table 12*Regression of Professional Usefulness on Frequency of Tasks Among the Teachers (All Writing Genres)*

Dependent Variables	Estimate	p-Value	R-Squared
Laboratory reports	-0.066	0.704	0.007
Technical reports	-0.121	0.505	0.023
Manuals	-0.110	0.645	0.011
Research articles	0.043	0.800	0.003
Job applications	0.123	0.334	0.047
Resume writing	-0.265	0.354	0.043
Expository writing	0.500	0.002	0.386
Essay assignments	0.471	0.026	0.224
Letters/emails	-0.009	0.977	0.000
Summary writing	0.377	0.063	0.162
Notes and minutes writing	0.435	0.009	0.293
Persuasive writing	0.450	0.058	0.168
Proposal for grants etc.	0.333	0.126	0.113

5. Discussion

The three groups, in the form of students, managerial engineers and operational engineers, were compared in terms of their responses to various statements by applying ANOVA using the IBM SPSS Software package and XL-STAT. From Table 1, it appears that excluding in case of "frequency of the writing task of manuals", "frequency of writing task of job applications", "frequency of writing task of essay assignments", and "frequency of writing task of minutes writing", the response to all the other statements differed significantly concerning the three groups (students, managerial engineers & professional engineers) as indicated by significant F-values at 0.01 level of significance (p -values ≤ 0.01). Accordingly, post-hoc analysis was carried out, and means were compared wherever the differences were found to be significant. Consequently, the observed mean differences were visualized in the form of Means plots that follow:

The analysis of variance showed wide variations in the perceptions of the managerial and operational engineers, students, and teachers on the frequency of tasks under various writing genres and their relative professional importance. Lowie and Seton (2013, p.106) suggest, "When the assumption of normality or equality is violated, we need to do a non-parametric test as an alternative to the one-way ANOVA. A good one is the Kruskal- Wallis H test.". Kruskal-Wallis's test, the non-parametric alternative of ANOVA, has also been applied to check if the results differed with and without the assumption of normality of the data. It was found that p-values arising from ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis tests were quite close to each other for most of the writing genres, and both led to the same conclusion for all of them, with the level of significance set at 5%. Thus, the null hypotheses " H_{02} : There is no significant difference between the different groups in terms of the frequency of writing tasks/ genres in the ESP classroom" and " H_{03} : There is no significant difference between the different groups in terms of the perceived usefulness of writing tasks/ genres in the ESP classroom," stood rejected.

According to the managerial engineers, technical report writing got the highest emphasis in the course, and proposal writing was the least. The operational engineers thought that drafting letters and emails and proposal writing deserved the highest and least attention, respectively. Writing laboratory reports and preparing resumes were, respectively, the most and least frequented tasks as perceived by the current students. The teachers placed the highest priority on drafting letters and emails and the least on proposal writing. The results of ANOVA and corresponding p-values are given in Table 4.

The rank correlations between the perceptions of managerial and operational engineers on the frequency of tasks, as reflected by their grading of the various writing genres, were quite high (0.872), and the teachers, too, had high correlations with each of them (0.930) and (0.833), respectively). This implies that the three groups bore similar perceptions of the frequency of tasks for various writing genres. The current students, on the contrary, had a rank correlation of (0.303) with the managerial engineers, (0.290) with the operational engineers, and (0.125) with the teachers implying that their perceptions were grossly different from the others. Table 5 shows the rank correlations (frequency of tasks) between the groups. The same results prevailed with the perceived importance of the writing genres in the professional field. ANOVA suggested significantly varying perceptions among the four different groups. Both the managerial and operational engineers thought drafting letters and emails had the highest professional importance and writing laboratory reports had the least. Teachers, too, felt that drafting letters and emails was the most needed writing genre in the professional area; however, writing the proposals was the least, according to them. In the perceptions of the current students, the professional field demanded writing laboratory reports the most and expository writing the least. The results of ANOVA are given in Table 6. Like the frequency of tasks, the managerial and operational engineers also bore a resemblance in their perceptions of the professional importance of the writing genres. They had a rank correlation of (0.745) between themselves. Interestingly, the perceptions of the current students negatively correlated with both; (-0.439) with the managerial students and (-0.302) with the operational engineers). Teachers' perceptions were poorly correlated with all of them; however, it was positive, and the lowest was with the operational engineers, as seen in Table 7. Average grading for the frequency of tasks and professional importance as done by the managerial and operational engineers, students, and teachers for each writing genre has been summarized in Figure 7 (in three parts). The figures show the difference in the perceptions of four categories of respondents in respect of both the frequency of tasks and professional importance. The figures also help us compare the grading difference between the frequency of tasks and professional importance by each category of respondents and for each writing genre. To check the correlation between the grading of professional importance and the frequency of the task, linear regressions were fitted with the former as the dependent variable and the latter as an independent variable. The linear regression was run for each group and writing genre. If the frequency of tasks for a particular writing genre positively correlates with its professional importance as perceived by working engineers, students, and teachers, then the coefficient of regression is expected to be quite high and significantly greater than zero.

Interestingly, it was observed that the coefficients of regression were high and significantly higher than zero for all writing genres among the students, implying that their perceptions of professional importance were based on the frequency of tasks they experienced in the course. The coefficients were also high and significantly higher than zero for most of the writing genres (nine of thirteen) among the operational engineers. But the coefficients were significant for very few writing genres among the managerial engineers (four of thirteen) and teachers (three of thirteen).

This probably revealed inconsistencies in their perceptions that what they thought was important was not taught in the course. The coefficients of regression with corresponding p-values are given in Tables 4 to 8

6. Conclusions and recommendations

This study was undertaken when the old syllabus of MAKAUT was in vogue.[29]. It is pertinent to mention that the old syllabus till 2018 was replaced with a new one in 2019. [30]. A glance at the two writing syllabuses (Appendixes D and E) shows that the new syllabus is more detailed and better-organized, keeping in mind the concepts of gradation, and thus, there are some elements in

both the new syllabus of the university and the current course design. This perhaps could be regarded as the strongest justification and corroboration of this study as this course also focuses on details and gradation. However, even the new syllabus does not pay enough attention to workplace writing needs, for example, in terms of various genres. Not all the genres that were considered useful by professional engineers are listed in the new syllabus. It is hoped that the teachers are aware of this gap and they would reduce the gap through classroom instruction.

This study found some similarities and differences with the study of Changpueng and Pattanapichet (2015). It is pertinent to mention that in addition to the perceived importance of various writing genres in the workplace, which was also done by Changpueng and Pattanapichet (2015), the present study also assessed the class room frequency of the teaching of those writing genres, and this is exclusive to only the present study. It was found in the study of Changpueng and Pattanapichet (2015) that inquiries, reports, and minutes of meetings were the first three important genres for engineering students. ESP teachers saw inquiries, memos, and reports as the first three important genres. The first three important genres for operational engineers encompassed requests, inquiries, and reports, while the first three important genres for managerial engineers were also requests, inquiries, and reports.[7]. In the present study, to the managerial engineers, technical report writing got the highest emphasis in the course, and proposal writing was the least. The operational engineers thought that drafting letters and emails and proposal writing deserved the highest and least attention, respectively. Writing laboratory reports and preparing resumes were, respectively, the most and least frequented tasks as perceived by the current students. The teachers placed the highest priority on drafting letters and emails and the least on proposal writing

The current university course revealed a mismatch between both the students' perceptions of what was needed and what the professional engineers wrote at their workplace. For example, persuasive writing is not a part of the university syllabus, but the managerial engineer needs it a lot, and even the operational engineers, particularly the IT engineers, need it when they write to their clients to highlight their credentials and expertise to bag the order in a competitive business environment.

7. Limitations

The scale of the analysis was constrained because of the small sample size of the teachers, who were important respondents. Consequently, the findings of the study might not be suitable for large-scale utilization. Many students could not take part in the research because the course was not part of the engineering curriculum. The downside is that they can only report the true effect of the course once they apply the learning at the workplace or in an academic setting.

The present study could not delve deep into ESP teacher motivation and attitude issues for time constraints though it is also to be considered an important factor in teaching/ learning.

The gap between the number of students and teachers and between students and professional engineers was high. On practical considerations, an engineering college fetched data from around 60 students on average, whereas the same college fetched data from only two ESP teachers. Hence, a large gap is seen between the numbers of these two categories of respondents. However, the gap was sought to be bridged through Tukey's HSD post hoc test.

8. Suggestions for future research

The wide gaps between the four groups in the perceptual difference to various components of ESP and particularly in terms of the frequency of the genres taught in the classroom and their relative usefulness in the workplace, necessitate a triangulated needs analysis in designing an ESP course in the future. The difference between the instructor and recipient and between the old recipient and the new recipient of classroom instruction has been proved by this study. Hence it is recommended that all subsequent studies on needs analysis and course design, particularly in ESP contexts, should include all the stakeholders, and this would make the course more effective and relevant to the workplace needs of the students. This would also improve the motivation levels of the students. The NEP (2020) also lays stress this aspect as it proposes "closer collaborations between industry and higher education institutions to drive innovation and research in these fields" (p.50).

Finally, autonomy can be granted to individual universities/ colleges to update/ upgrade their writing skill courses from time to time, keeping in mind the dynamic needs of academics and particularly the industry, which is changing rapidly in the new millennium. Hyland's contention is very significant regarding the future, "Predictions are never easy, but one certainty is that ESP's concern with mapping the discourses and communicative challenges of the modern workplace and classroom will continue." (2013, p. 107).

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Publisher's Note: All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of their affiliated organizations, or those of the publisher, the editors and the reviewers.

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Appendix- A

Student's questionnaire

<p>1. Please rate the frequency of the following writing tasks in English in your engineering course.</p> <p>a) Laboratory Reports b) Technical Reports c) Manuals d) Research Articles e) Job Applications f) Resume Writing g) Expository Writing (Explaining/ Describing) h) Essay Assignments i) Letters/ emails j) Summary writing k) Note-taking/ Minutes writing l) Persuasive writing m) Proposal (for grants etc.)</p>	<p>A lot Sometimes Rarely Not even once</p>
<p>2. How useful do you think the following writing tasks will be in your professional life?</p> <p>a) Laboratory Reports b) Technical Reports c) Manuals d) Research Articles e) Job Applications f) Resume Writing g) Expository Writing (Explaining/ Describing) h) Essay Assignments i) Letters/ emails j) Summary writing k) Note-taking/ Minutes writing l) Persuasive writing m) Proposal (for grants etc.)</p>	<p>Highly useful Useful Useful to some extent Not very useful Not at all useful</p>

Appendix- B

Professional engineer's questionnaire

<p>1. Please rate the frequency of the following writing tasks in English in your engineering course.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Laboratory Reports b) Technical Reports c) Manuals d) Research Articles e) Job Applications f) Resume Writing g) Expository Writing (Explaining/ Describing) h) Essay Assignments i) Letters/ emails j) Summary writing k) Note-taking/ Minutes writing l) Persuasive writing m) Proposal (for grants etc.) 	<p>A lot Sometimes Rarely Not even once</p>
<p>2. How useful do you think the following writing tasks are in your professional life?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Laboratory Reports b) Technical Reports c) Manuals d) Research Articles e) Job Applications f) Resume Writing g) Expository Writing (Explaining/ Describing) h) Essay Assignments i) Letters/ emails j) Summary writing k) Note-taking/ Minutes writing l) Persuasive writing m) Proposal (for grants etc.) 	<p>Highly useful Useful Useful to some extent Not very useful Not at all useful</p>

Appendix- C

Teacher's questionnaire

<p>1. Please rate the frequency of the following writing tasks in English in your engineering course.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Laboratory Reports b) Technical Reports c) Manuals d) Research Articles e) Job Applications f) Resume Writing g) Expository Writing (Explaining/ Describing) h) Essay Assignments i) Letters/ emails j) Summary writing k) Note-taking/ Minutes writing l) Persuasive writing m) Proposal (for grants etc.) n) Any other (Free Writing) 	<p>A lot Sometimes Rarely Not even once</p>
<p>2. How useful do you think will the following writing tasks be in the professional life of your students?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Laboratory Reports b) Technical Reports c) Manuals d) Research Articles e) Job Applications f) Resume Writing g) Expository Writing (Explaining/ Describing) h) Essay Assignments i) Letters/ era JJ j) Summary writing k) Note-taking/ Minutes writing l) Persuasive writing m) Proposal (for grants etc.) n) Any other 	<p>Highly useful Useful Useful to some extent Not very useful Not at all useful</p>

Appendix- D

(English writing skill syllabus of MAKAUT, West Bengal -New- From the 2018 version, p.31).

http://makautexam.net/aicte_details/Syllabus/BTECH.pdf

Detailed contents

1. Vocabulary Building

- 1.1 The concept of Word Formation: Compounding, Backformation, Clipping, Blending.
- 1.2 Root words from foreign languages and their use in English
- 1.3 Acquaintance with prefixes and suffixes from foreign languages in English to form derivatives.
- 1.4 Synonyms, antonyms, and standard abbreviations: Acronyms

2. Basic Writing Skills

- 2.1 Sentence Structures & Types: Simple, Compound, Complex
- 2.2 Use of phrases and clauses in sentences: Transformation of sentences, active, passive, narration
- 2.3 Importance of proper punctuation
- 2.4 Creating coherence: Arranging paragraphs & Sentences in a logical order
- 2.5 Creating Cohesion: Organizing principles of paragraphs in documents
- 2.6 Techniques for writing precisely

3. Identifying Common Errors in Writing

- 3.1 Subject-verb agreement
- 3.2 Noun-pronoun agreement
- 3.3 Misplaced modifiers
- 3.4 Articles
- 3.5 Prepositions
- 3.6 Redundancies
- 3.7 Cliches

4. Nature and Style of Sensible Writing

- 4.1 Describing
- 4.2 Defining
- 4.3 Classifying
- 4.4 Providing examples or evidence
- 4.5 Writing introduction and conclusion

5. Writing Practices

- 5.1 Comprehension
- 5.2 Précis Writing
- 5.3 Essay Writing
- 5.4 Business Letter, Cover Letter & CV; E-mail

Appendix- E

(English writing skill syllabus of MAKAUT, West Bengal -Old- Adapted from 2007 version.p.3)

https://makautwb.ac.in/syllabus/Engineering_Syllabus_of_First_Year_old.pdf

Writing

Selecting material for expository, descriptive, and argumentative pieces, business letters; formal reports; summarizing and abstracting; expressing ideas within a restricted word limit; paragraph division; the introduction and the conclusion; listing reference material; use of charts, graphs, and tables; punctuation and spelling; semantics of connectives, modifiers, and modals; variety in sentences and paragraphs.

Grammar

Correction of sentences, vocabulary/ word formation, Single word for a group of words, Fill in the blank, transformation of sentences, Structure of sentences – Active / Passive Voice – direct / Indirect Narration.

Distribution of marks

Examination

Letters, including official – 10

Precis- 10

Comprehension (chart/ paragraph) – 10

Reporting writing, including technical/ scientific -10

Essay – 10.

Grammar- 20.

Total- 70.